

HEALTH AND WELLBEING IMPACT OF INDOOR LIGHTING INTERVENTIONS

POLICY BRIEF

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CREDITS

This policy is part of an outreach research developed in the framework of ENLIGHTENme. It has been authored by Dr Daan R van der Veen, MSc Débora Barroggi Constantino, Prof Debra J Skene (USURREY), Dr Marijke Gordijn (C@W), Dr David McDaid (LSE), and MSc Anne Landvreugd (VUA).

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HIGHLIGHTS

- **Many costs of not taking action:** Poor light exposure is associated with multiple adverse impacts such as increased risks of depression, problems sleeping and accidents. Inappropriate outdoor lighting may also, for example, make locations less appealing, reducing the sense of community and intergenerational connections. All of these adverse impacts can have substantial economic costs.
- **Health and wellbeing impact:** Light is an inescapable environmental factor that can have a significant impact on health and wellbeing, including attention/performance and mood, safety, circadian rhythms, quality of life, subjective happiness, and sleep. Considering the timing, quality and availability of good light potentially also has economic benefits, as it may protect health and wellbeing, and help avoid substantial costs to health systems and the wider society.
- **Biological clocks:** Good light exposure involves maximizing light exposure in a comfortable way during the day and minimizing light exposure at night to improve daily rhythms and sleep quality. However, factors such as personal safety, reading, and social interactions often necessitate night-time light exposure which can conflict with good light exposure. Furthermore, everybody is different with large variations in light sensitivity and 24-hour (circadian) rhythmicity in sleep and wake, requiring personalized optimization.
- **Vulnerable groups:** Older adults in particular are at higher risk of poor light exposure due to age-related changes to light perception and behaviour. Risks for the general population of increased night-time light exposure are also escalating due to an increase in the use of LEDs, screen exposure (TV, mobile phones, computers), and shift-work schedules.
- **Recommendations:** Increase daytime light exposure in public and private spaces including offices, and increase awareness of the importance of good light hygiene: more light during the day, less light at night.

AIM

This policy brief aims to guide municipal policymakers, urban planners, and health policymakers in defining priorities in their lighting policy development by considering indoor and outdoor light exposure that optimises health and wellbeing outcomes.

BACKGROUND

Light is an inescapable environmental factor that can potentially impact health. It has many direct influences, including on visual perception, mood, alertness, vitamin D synthesis, and sleep. Light can also potentially impact some people's wellbeing, such as subjective happiness and quality of life. Light also shapes the character of urban spaces, contributing to both private and public environments. The quality of light is key to its effectiveness and tolerability. Aspects such as spectral composition, flicker, and glare from poorly designed lighting can cause discomfort and reduce visual clarity. Importantly, the timing and quality of light exposure (intensity, spectral composition) play a central role in regulating people's biological clocks, which govern 24-hour (circadian) rhythms. These rhythms are crucial for almost every aspect of behaviour and physiology. Disrupting them increases the risk of sleep problems, obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and mood disorders. Urban residents often experience insufficient exposure to bright light during the day and excessive light at night. Key challenges that lead to daytime light deficiencies include small windows that prevent sufficient natural daylight exposure, complicated by an increase in indoor and sedentary lifestyles. Artificial indoor lighting often also lacks the intensity and appropriate spectral composition needed for biological clock synchronisation. This problem is exacerbated in older adults because natural aging leads to reduced light perception caused by yellowing of the lens and loss of photoreceptors and spending more time indoors. Key challenges that lead to overexposure to light during night-time include high levels of artificial lighting to, for instance, create ambiance, increase safety and facilitate reading and social interactions. In recent years this problem has increased due to an escalating use of handheld devices such as phones and tablets.

For some, this leads to delayed sleep onset, poor sleep quality, and long-term health risks. A particular risk group includes night shift workers, who typically represent up to 15-25% of the workforce, such as health care professionals, fire and policing teams and factory/warehouse workers. Remedying these issues as part of municipal policy, making use of effective lighting interventions is both feasible and potentially highly cost-effective. The cost of health conditions, such as depression and poor sleep, associated with poor lighting are substantial. Across the EU the annual costs of mood problems, including depression and anxiety, many of which are preventable, are at least 4% of all EU economic output (GDP). Similarly a recent study estimated that the annual economic costs of poor sleep was almost 2% of GDP in both Germany and the UK. Small reductions in these and other health impacts due to better lighting policies can make a big difference.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To implement these insights in municipal policy we recommend careful consideration of light intensity and quality (blue-enriched, glare) for light in public spaces and offices. In cases where municipal services are involved with people's home environment (e.g., health care visitors), raising awareness and messaging around good light hygiene (bright light during the day and dim light at night) is a cheap and straightforward intervention that could even include the provision of a blue-enriched light source for self-guided use.

Recommendations:

- Increase awareness through health messaging of the importance of good light hygiene based on daytime exposure to bright, natural daylight and reduction of evening and night-time bright light exposure
- Develop public spaces with ample natural light exposure, such as parks and open plazas, and provide abundant windows and bright light in public spaces and offices.
- Prioritise lighting improvements for older adults , such as through assessments of lighting within their own homes, as well as in assisted living/residential care homes or hospitals.
- Support policies to optimise light exposure for shift workers through smart workplace adaptations and adopting improved shift-work rotation schedules.
- Adopt an evidence-based approach: recording light quality and exposure in public spaces should become a standard part of a municipality decision-making process.

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